

INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES AS AN OBJECT OF EFFICIENCY COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE ACQUISITION

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Abstract

The informatization of education based on the use of information and communication technologies is aimed at activating and accelerating the learning process, implementing the ideas of developmental learning, improving the forms and methods of organizing learning, and ensuring the transition from memorization to independent assimilation of new knowledge. The article considers ways how students can develop their communicative competence through IT means.

Keywords: ICT, competence, communication, English language, teaching and learning, information technologies.

The informatization of education based on the use of information and communication technologies is aimed at activating and accelerating the learning process, implementing the ideas of developmental learning, improving the forms and methods of organizing learning, and ensuring the transition from memorization to independent assimilation of new knowledge. ICTs provide teachers and students with the ability to operate, store, process and retrieve information, encourage independent and active learning and personal responsibility for learning, and motivate teachers and students to continue learning even outside school hours.

The use of information and communication technologies will increase the student's motivation and desire for learning. This not only includes working with a computer, which contributes to increasing the student's interest in learning, it is also the ability to adjust the presentation of various problems by difficulty levels, encouraging correct answers automatically and quickly, while not resorting to moralizing and censure, which in turn contributes to the loss of motivation of the student to study. The use of information and communication technologies in the educational process makes it possible to individualize and delimit the learning process, realizing an interactive dialogue with students, giving everyone the opportunity to choose their own mode of learning activities. As a rule, in each class there are children with both high and low levels of development.

Now everyone understands that the Internet has tremendous informational capabilities and equally impressive services. It is necessary to use modern learning opportunities in teaching and improving the English language. There are many learning sites on the Internet that you can attend to receive lectures and language lessons; communicate online with a language teacher, with native speakers; participate in group discussions; use vocabulary and grammar; determine your level of knowledge with the help of various language tests; view video; get access to many electronic publications in English; read comments after articles in English; replenish and expand vocabulary; have access to current information that is updated every day; save time and money.

Due to the Internet development the chance of the English studying has grown up extremely. Because of

the common usage of the English language in different parts of the world, there is huge information in, which also make a teaching role. It is the Internet that is considered the technical breakthrough of the last decades, which has had a very strong influence on the development of educational technologies. Besides the fact that a lot of hints and educational documents are posted on different websites, the technical abilities of the Internet give a chance held lessons in English from the network. In the network you can find almost all the teaching materials for learning English, online tests and animated materials. These are used in language learning in any places. The possibility to find proper material in one clicks help students to improve English skills speaking. Using Internet, a student can communicate with original citizen of different countries and representatives of different peoples. By another words there isn't only their language skills upgrading, but their English language abilities with various nations. Due to such an online help in communication, it is not necessary for a student to use simulating program or communicative games, because he has already presented in online conversation. Also, many English teachers recommend using the Internet to manipulate speech etiquette formulas, because with live communication, speech etiquette is absorbed faster because you find yourself in a real language environment.

We can use the Internet:

- for independent search of information in the framework of the work on the topic of the lesson;
- for self-study, deepening, closing a gap in knowledge, skills, and abilities;
- for self-preparation for the exam [1, p.255].

This problem can be solved using modern multimedia technologies. Most of the classrooms in our university are equipped with modern technical means (computers, video projectors, interactive boards, televisions, language equipment, etc.) and teachers are working on testing new educational technologies in practical classes and during self-training of students using a large number of online components and Internet resources.

Intellectual educational technologies assume the integration of the most effective educational technologies into a complete system

The main feature and distinctive feature of teaching students in innovation-type universities is the focus

on the training of scientific personnel capable of developing the university's scientific potential, as well as meeting the needs of the knowledge-intensive sector of the economy. Within the framework of innovative educational projects of leading universities, programs are implemented for the active use of intelligent educational technologies, which imply the need to communicate the educational, scientific and practical tasks being solved, and the diversity of cooperation between teachers and students [2, p.99].

With such a target setting, cognitive universal actions are one of the leading components of the educational standard. In this regard, cognitive universal actions include:

information retrieval actions;

the ability to navigate in the system of knowledge and to realize the need for new knowledge;

the ability to pre-select sources of information to search for new knowledge.

Before we start to analyze multimedia resources first of all we need to give the definition of the term multimedia technologies and "digital technologies". Central to our study are the concepts of "multimedia technology" and "digital technology".

According to E.S. Polat multimedia technology, is "a set of computer technologies that simultaneously use several information media: graphics, text, video, animation, sound effects" [3, p.316]. In other words, multimedia involves information from different forms, using sound, graphics, video, animation etc. It is worth noting that today the Internet acts as a qualitatively new media, combining all existing (video, text, audio, graphics). According to D.Crystal all these elements act as a single communicative act, and therefore they should be considered in aggregate, and not separately from each other [4, p.57].

The term "digital technologies" today is interpreted term. Initially, this term was used to refer to technologies containing binary code. However, due to the widespread use of personal computers and mobile devices, the word "digital" has become widely used. The term "digital technologies" in the framework of the theory of language teaching refers to all types of technologies associated with the computers usage and portable electronic devices (tablets, smart phones, etc.). Digital technologies include electronic tools, devices, systems, and resources that produce, store, or process information in various formats.

Working on students' communicative competence in school lessons, it is necessary to headline some high significant points: for in reaching educational quality via IT usage, for providing the possibilities to acquire such conversational skills that used in live situations.

In the secondary school studying the most important focus is the development skills in making spontaneous conversation unlike grammar structures which are presented related on any theme of spoken English language.

The problems of the impact of modern information and communication technologies (ICT) in educational process and their effective use in teaching foreign languages are considered in the works of researchers M.A. Bovtenko, R.K.Potapova, E.S.Polat, P.V.Sysoev, M.N.

Evstigneev, A.V.Zubov, R.K.Piotrovskaya, R.G. Piotrovsky, A.V. Khutskiy. In Western science, the informatization of the process of learning foreign languages formed the basis of research by G.Dudeney, M.Pegrum, D.Boyd, D.Crystal, M.Warshauer, M.Levy.

Nevertheless, due to the technical progress and the emergence of new types of multimedia and digital technologies against the background of a change in educational paradigms, the practice of using these technologies is still ahead of theory. Moreover, existing research in this area is mainly focused on the methodology of teaching foreign language in adults. However, analysis of the literature in the field of psychology and pedagogy (L.Vygotsky, D.B.Elkonin, L.I.Bozhovich) showed that the younger school age is the most important stage of human development, which forms the basis of a conscious cognitive interest in learning. Moreover, the empirical experience of the authors of this study proved the increased interest of the younger generation in the use of multimedia and digital technologies, including for educational purposes.

Also we analyzed the 70s or 80s years XX century for understanding the situation of development of the linguistic component in Kazakhstani secondary school, which were set in the context of globalization, based on oral and written communication. Due to development of Information technologies there is a lack of language for understanding new material, which can be studied via different resources.

For remaining up-to-date with evolving technology our society has taken the effective studying letters – Information and Communications Technologies (ICT). The main merits of ICT are to improve an access of education, which improve again the system of modern specialist developing. Interactive self-work gives students the opportunity not only to develop their language skills, but also to develop their effective intellectual part, communicative competence and critical and didactical thinking. Emotional regulation of the students' mental process is the biggest task of foreign language lecturers. It means the existing of motivation - positive emotional communication of learners. Everyday integration of internet resources into self-studying process gives an opportunity for affordable education, to form a system its self and to create a qualified professional [5, p.25].

The most useful approach of communicative competence drafting during teaching professional language is the use of IT means. Such an approach is the most modern one, which improves all used before in order to reconstruct the English reaching language particular and the education in common.

With the widespread personal devices such as tape recorders and film projectors the active integration of technical equipment into the educational process dates back to the 1970s. Such technical equipment gave a place to sophisticated device – a personal computer. In its turn, this event led to a separate type of research - linguodidactics emergence, which sets itself narrower goals and objectives.

The twentieth century, a new approach to learning foreign languages - CALL - Computer Assisted Language Learning (language learning using a computer).

In the 90s. In the twentieth century, in connection with the development of the Internet, different approaches emerge from CALL: TELL (Technology Enhanced Language Learning - technology-enhanced language learning) and ICT in LT (ICT in language teaching) reflecting changes in the field of high technology - the

emergence of the Internet and electronic communication. The emergence and development of mobile communications, which were actively used in linguodidactics, led in turn to the emergence of the term MALL - Mobile Assisted Language Learning (language learning using mobile communications) [6, p.36-39]. See figure 1.

Fig 1. Development of approaches in foreign language learning

In modern linguo-didactic, CALL is one of the most advanced research direction for scientists of different fields: psychologists, methodologists, programmers, linguists, etc. The issue of integrating ICT into the educational process of teaching foreign languages is permanently discussed in professional forums and conferences (for example, EUROCALL, CALICO, ICETC and others). Pointed interest on this question led to the emergence of periodic publishing of this topic (in particular, "Information and communication technologies in education", "Computer tools in education", "Telecommunications and informatization of education", ON-CALL, Language Learning and Technology, etc.)

Thus based on the above we can denote following list of technical means, which help to intensify the educational process in teaching English language. There beyond are:

- 1) Multimedia technology, which combined the ability to play and record speech and interactive video;
- 2) hypertext creating a system of cross-references in text files of information;
- 3) hypermedia, combined hypertext and multimedia;

These tools allow you to use a computer to work on all types of speech activity: to develop not only reading and writing skills, but also listening and speaking skills (including such aspects as pronunciation and intonation), as well as for real communication with native speakers of the language being studied orally and writing.

After doing data analyzing of ICT we came close to our main goal of learning a foreign language for the formation of communicative competence through computer and multimedia means.

The communicative competence drafting include the possibility of mutual activity, based on IT means. Millions people in all over the world have the opportunity to have different conversation, for huge variety of themes such a: cultural, political, social and others. The most interesting thing in it, that people do not need to have conservative face to face communication, but can see each other via special programs and work together on language skills acquisition. Work by using internet during the English lesson we simulate model of real communication. From psychological point of view on this question-when a learner communicate in a true language environment provided by the Internet, students keeps his real life surroundings unlike face to face communication. Because when a learner starts communicate with real person in life it can be very stressful for him to begin some conversation for the first time. Having such a dialog via internet massagers it is more confidently for him. Involved in solving a wide range of meaningful, realistic, interesting and achievable tasks, students learn to respond spontaneously and adequately to them, which stimulates the creation of original statements, and not routine manipulation of language formulas.

Primary importance is focused on understanding, transmission and expression the meaning, which motivates the students bring their words stock for the target conversation. In other words learners are fixed on forms usage, but not on them only, grammar studying goes on in conversation, namely in live communication, excluding a pure grinding of grammatical rules.

For students development communicative competence, having IT means is extremely important, because of the absence of some negative comments, which lead to the language divide. Computer provides

independence and confident conditions for better development of language skills keeping students individuality.

Information assets are directly connected to the education advancement. That means Internet is put about all means and determine education evolution with its place in whole future of humankind. To have successful navigation in the world infomedia, learners should skill information and also computer-screen cultures, for searching different materials properly.

Being an information space international web has huge enormous variety of assets and resources. Here after some basic opportunities for development of communicative competence: e-mail;

- ✓ teleconference
- ✓ video conferencing;
- ✓ the ability to publish your own information, creating your own homepage;
- ✓ access to information resources:
- ✓ reference directories (Yahoo!, InfoSeek / Ultra Smart, Look Smart, Galaxy);
- ✓ search engines (Alta Vista, Hot Bob, Open Text, WebCrawler, Excite);
- ✓ conversation in the network (Chat).

1. These resources can be actively used during the English lesson.

2. Communicative and intercultural competence acquisition is impossible without practice of communication! The usage of Internet resources in a foreign (English) language lesson is highly important: the virtual Internet environment allows you to go beyond the temporal and spatial frameworks, allowing its users to authentically communicate. However, we must not forget that the Internet is only an auxiliary technical tool

of education, and in order to achieve optimal results, it is necessary to correctly integrate its use into the lesson process.

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